

Socio-Political and Educational Reforms of Robert Sandeman in Balochistan'

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Abstract

Present study was carried out so as to determine the socio-political and educational reforms of Robert Sandeman in Balochistan. In this regard, the descriptive research design was used. University of Balochistan and Sardar Bahadur Khan Women's University (Social Science Division or Faculty) were selected as purposively. Keeping in the view objective of the this study, two hundred (200) respondents among them 100 respondents were selected from the University of Balochistan and similar, 100 respondents were selected from the Sardar Bahadur Khan Women's University Quetta. Analysis of variance, One-Way, ANOVA (LSD) test was applied so that to determine the perceived perceptions of the respondents at 0.01 alpha level. In this regard, the null hypotheses were also used. The finding reveals that more than half 54% of the respondents had fall in up to 30 year of age. More than half 56% of the respondents were having the M.Sc., or MA degree, more than half (56%) of respondents by gender were male. null hypothesis 1 was rejected at $p \leq 0.05$; .01 alpha level. However, null hypothesis 2 was accepted and alternate hypothesis was accepted based on perceived perception of groups. Similar, null hypothesis was rejected and alternate hypothesis was accepted based on respondent's received perceptions at $p \leq 0.05$; .01 alpha level, that were ($M = 3.50$ "UoB", $M = 3.49$ "SKBWU") were found non-significant differences.

Keywords: educational, Sir Robert Sandeman, Socio-political, Balochistan

Introduction

Balochistan region as area-wise is the largest [provinces of Pakistan](#) and situated in the South-western region of the country. Quetta is the biggest city and provincial capital. Balochistan province consisting to shares its borders with Sindh province east and southeast, [Khyber Pakhtunkhwa](#) and the [Punjab](#) to the northeast, [Iran](#) to the west, the [Arabian Sea](#) to the south, and [Afghanistan](#) is located to the north and northwest.

Generally, the term [Balochistan](#) refers to "Land of the Baloch". Mainly under-privileged, and poorer portion of the country, natural resources as the dominated features of the [provincial economy](#). Particularly having the mammoth reservoir by the term of natural gas that estimated to have sufficient capacity over the medium to long term. Quetta, Hub and Gwadar Port are the major economic zones of the province. However, in this aspects, the Balochistan province is as renowned for its unique sort of norm, topography, culture and tremendously dry [desert weather](#) (Encyclopedia Britannica, 2017).

Balochistan province had occupied and located as the exact slice of the south-eastern areas in the Iranian Plateau. Background history of the province revealed that the agriculture occupation as the first recognized defrayals or livelihoods in the pre-Indus Valley Civilisation period. However, the Mehrgarh, prehistoric place (earliest civilisation around 7000 BC) was located in Balochistan province. However, the Balochistan province has distinct feature as areas-wise and westernmost extent of the earliest civilisation. However, in the era of 7th Century, the Islam entrance as the religion and faith.

The econ of the British Raj peculiarly, under the command of Robert Sandeman had historic educational improvement, social development and physical infrastructure restructuring scheme and structure, introduced an innovative system of tribal pacification in Balochistan were completed. But unfortunately, entire developmental structures and reform of the British Raj within colonial system just by ransacked the wealth and resources of Balochistan either quality aspects or quantitative quantum's. Therefore, present research or exploration was designed so as to determine the British Raj task or occupation, their exploitation policy and fulfilment of their demands through their agents.

So far Robert Sandeman had done great job about the restoration of peace and brining about prosperity and harmony in the social order system. Quite a bit of his impact with the Baluch clans was because of his propensity for continually managing them in the Baluch way and settling question as per their very own traditions. He utilized the Baluch clan leader at whatever point he could. Baluch horsemen for the most part framed his escorts, and offered themselves anxiously for the obligation. They preferred his well-looking highlights, and, in the lays of which they are so affectionate, the gestures

of recognition of "Sinniman" were sung in numerous a fringe rural. Be that as it may, in 1868 an overwhelming blow fell upon him.

Problem statement

Sir Robert Groves Sandman (1835–1892) was influential rulers in Balochistan, or a pacificator and a successful administrator, Colonial of British Indian officer and administrator. However, the Sir Robert Groves Sandman was introduced the diverse policies such as familiarized an innovative system of tribal pacification in Balochistan informally termed 'Sandemanization', that was in effect from 1877 to 1947, financial allowances to tribal chiefs or sardars and so forth as the policy worked admirably. In order to, make the contented of the masses the Sir Robert Groves Sandman uses the diverse policies and reforms in the three portion of Balochistan (e.g. Kalat State, British Balochistan and Leased Territories). Keeping in the view importance of the matter, the present research was stressed the Sir Robert Groves Sandman approaches regarding the socio-political empowerment, educational reforms and these policies and strategies impacts. In this regard, present research was also measures the Robert Sandeman policies how exploited to people of Balochistan by using the Sardari and Nawabi systems and how could these policies were executed or imposed at grass root level. Therefore present study was designed so as to determine the socio-political and educational reforms of Robert Sandeman in Balochistan.

Objectives

The specific objectives are:

- To find out the demographic information of the respondents

Hypothesis tested

Following hypotheses were operationalized:

H^1 : There will be no substantial discrepancies between the perceived perceptions of the participants concerning the Robert Sandeman ruled in Balochistan.

H^2 : There will be no substantial discrepancies between the perceived perceptions of the participants concerning the purpose of British Raj reforms to gain the trust of people.

H^3 : There will be no substantial discrepancies between the perceived perceptions of the participants concerning the British planned to rule and enslave the people for a long time.

Methodology

In present inquiry the descriptive research design was used. The descriptive type stressed the current nature and segment of demographic profile around depicting the idea and perception in which certain existing phenomenon occurred (Jonassen, 2001; and Trochim, 2000). Comparative small size and shape of the target population, the University of Balochistan and *Sardar Bahadur Khan Women's University* (Social Science Division of Faculty) were selected purposively. Keeping in the view objective of the this study, two hundred (200) respondents form (University of Balochistan and *Sardar Bahadur Khan Women's University Quetta*, the Social Science Division of Faculty) were selected as target population, among them 100 respondents were selected from the University of Balochistan and similar, 100 respondents were selected from the *Sardar Bahadur Khan Women's University Quetta*. The descriptive research type of research design within term of qualitative study was applied by using the convenience simple procedure. In this regard, both population were determined by using the table of Wunsch (1986) "selecting sample sizes from given population" at 0.01 percent error rate. At field level the raw data were collected and interviewed were conducted so as to answer the research questions (Miles & Huberman, 1994). Analysis of variance, One-Way, ANOVA (LSD) test was applied so that to determine the perceived perceptions of the respondents. Finally P-value was considered as the significance test and

useful measurement about to denote the strength of evidence against the null hypothesis testing and validity of research questions. In this regard, the p-value was measured and setup at 0.01 alpha level.

Results

Figure, 1, Demographic profile about age composition

Age of the respondents was categorized into three segments such as up to 30 years, 31 to 45 years and 46 and above. In this regard, the data was gathered and presented in figure-1. More than half 54% of the respondents had fall in up to 30 year of age, while most 34% of respondents were believed, that they had 31 to 45 years of age.

Figure, 2, Demographic profile about educational level

Education status of the respondents were classified into three parts such M.Sc. /MA. B.Sc. /BA and others. In this aspects of data was presented in figure-2. More than half 56% of the respondents were having the M.Sc., or MA degree. Whereas, most 23% of the respondents acquired the B.Sc., or BA degree.

Figure, 3. Demographic profile by gender

The results of the figure-3 shows that more than half (56%) of respondents by gender were male and 44% of respondents by gender were female.

Hypothesis tested

Following hypotheses were operationalized:

Table, 1. Comparison perceived score regarding Robert Sandeman ruled in Balochistan

H^1	UoB		SBKWU		Mean Square	p-value	Significant*
	Mean Score	S.D	Mean Score	S.D			
	1.77	.510	1.67	.493			

Note: = Significant at .01 level**. = Significant at .01 level*.

Analysis of variance was utilized so as to observe the variation perceptions between the groups. In this regard, the null hypothesis was tested, the hypothesis is “there will be no substantial discrepancies between the perceived perceptions of the participants concerning the Robert Sandeman ruled in Balochistan”. The alpha level was set on 0.01 level by using the LSD test. ANOVA results depicted that there were no statistically significant were found among the group perceptions. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and alternate hypothesis was accepted based on respondent’s perceived perception at $p \leq .00$; .01 alpha level. It was concluded that the perception variations were did not found between the groups as shown in table-1.

Table, 2. Comparison perceived score regarding purpose of British Raj reforms to gain the trust of people

H^2	UoB		SBKWU		Mean Square	p-value	Significant*
	Mean Score	S.D	Mean Score	S.D			
	3.60	.932	3.25	.999			

Note: = Significant at .01 level**. = Significant at .01 level*.

The main feature of the current research was to denote the perceived perception of the respondents as shown in table-2. In this regard, the null hypothesis was tested, the hypothesis is “there will be no substantial discrepancies between the perceived perceptions of the participants concerning the purpose of British Raj reforms to gain the trust of people?” the Likert type of scaling was used whereby ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The alpha level was setup at 0.01 level. The significant was observed between the group perceptions. Therefore, the null hypothesis 2 was accepted and alternate hypothesis was accepted based on perceived perception of groups.

Table, 3. Comparison perceived score regarding British planned to rule and enslave the people

H^3	UoB		SBKWU		Mean Square	p-value	Significant*
	Mean Score	S.D	Mean Score	S.D			
	3.50	.969	3.49	.948			

Note: = Significant at .01 level**. = Significant at .01 level*.

The outcome of the present table-3, were shown that non-significant variations within perception observed between two group perceptions. In this regard the statistically significant differences at the $p \leq .01$; .001 were found among the perception of the two groups. The hypothesis is “there will be no substantial discrepancies between the perceived perceptions of the participants concerning the British planned to rule and enslave the people for a long time” Therefore,

the null hypothesis was rejected and alternate hypothesis was accepted based on respondent's received perceptions at $p \leq .00$; .01 alpha level, that were ($M = 3.50$ "UoB", $M = 3.49$ "SKBWU") were found non-significant differences.

Conclusion

The Robert Sandeman had bring the desirable and historic changes in educational dynamics, social dimension and physical infrastructure. Beside that Sir Robert Sandeman introduced an innovative system of tribal pacification in Balochistan. Due to the Sir Robert Sandeman efforts and results the peace restoration, prosperity and harmony prevailed in the Balochistan state. Colonel Sir [Robert Groves Sandeman](#) genius individual who had familiarised in 1877 to 1947 an innovative system of tribal pacification in Balochistan.

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